

ORIGINAL PAPER

Prophylactic and acute treatment with the homeopathic medicine *Betula* 30c for birch pollen allergy: a double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled study of consistency of VAS responses

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A study of the consistency of responses by allergic patients in repeated studies of the homeopathic remedy *Betula* 30c or placebo against birch pollen allergy, was made. A randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial was performed including participants with a known allergy to birch pollen. Allergy symptoms were assessed on a visual analogue scale (VAS) by patients or parents each day during a 20-day period during two different pollen seasons. The work was carried out in Oslo, Norway during May 1995, 1996 and 1997. There were 51 patients ranging in age from 7 to 50 y. The homeopathic remedy *Betula* 30c or placebo was given as tablets, both as a prophylactic agent, once a week for 4 weeks before the pollen season started, and as an acute remedy during the pollen season. The mean value of the symptom scores on the visual analogue scale, for all registration days from each patient was the main outcome. The patient groups that received either placebo or *Betula* 30c for two successive years showed a consistent response ($r=0.75$, $P=0.01$ and $r=0.70$, $P=0.003$, respectively). No such correlation was found in the two groups that changed remedy from one year to another (either from placebo to *Betula* or vice versa). Subjective assessment of allergic symptoms to birch pollen differed more from one year to another when different regimens (placebo or homeopathic) had been administered these two seasons, than when the same treatment had been given. *British Homeopathic Journal* (2001) 90, 73–78.

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Introduction

Therapeutic effects of homeopathic immunotherapy (HIT) of allergic disorders has been reported by Reilly *et al.*^{1–4} The difference between HIT and ordinary immunotherapy⁵ is the very high dilution of the allergen used in homeopathy. The key issue is whether such a highly diluted substance can have any effect on

humans. To substantiate or refute positive findings like those of Reilly *et al* we have studied a single substance, *Betula* (pollen from Birch), diluted according to homeopathic procedures to a degree (30c which is a dilution of 10^{-60}) that nothing of the original substance could be present in the final remedy. The two previous trials, performed in 1995 and 1996, were both randomized, double-blind and placebo-controlled.^{6,7} In the first, we gave the remedy as an acute treatment during the birch pollen season, and found relief of symptoms in the *Betula* 30c group. Because some patients in this group reported aggravation of symptoms, possibly due to the tablets, we wanted to repeat the study in a slightly different way. We included a new group of allergic patients, changed

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the instructions concerning tablet use, and also altered the study design with respect to period and mode of registration. The results were surprising in that the *Betula* group suffered more complaints than the placebo group during the only three days with pollen this year. This follow-up study (1996) was not conclusive, because a cold and rainy spring led to a low pollen exposure. Therefore, we decided to repeat the study a third time, asking patients from the two previous studies to participate once more. Patients from both previous studies—being unaware of which kind of treatment they would receive, whether *Betula* or placebo—were then randomized into new groups, receiving either *Betula* or placebo.

The main aim of this third study (1997) was different from those of the former two. We wanted to investigate the consistency of subjective judgments, ie how patients would score their allergy symptoms in two different years, on a visual analogue scale (VAS). Thus, we wanted to examine whether patients would react similarly when receiving the same remedy (*Betula* or placebo) during the two pollen seasons, but differently to different remedies. No power analysis was performed to decide the number of patients needed; this was simply a comparison study at an individual level. To the best of our knowledge, such a 'consistency check' of the VAS method applied to symptoms of allergy has not been published. This motivated the present investigation.

participate in the 1997 trial, they were aware of whether they had received *Betula* or placebo in the first trial. Those who participated in 1996 were invited to attend the new trial, without the 1996 code being broken until the 1997 trial and its analysis had been completed (Figure 1).

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The selection of patients was done in 1995 and 1996. Only patients from these two trials were asked to participate. The initial inclusion/exclusion criteria were:

- Persons of both sexes, age 7–50 y, having a clear history of birch pollen allergy confirmed with a positive skin prick test were included.
- Excluded were persons with diseases of any kind other than allergy (also eczema and asthma). With conditions causing nasal blockage (polyps, septum deviation, chronic oedema due to perennial rhinitis). Individuals taking all sorts of medication (oral contraceptives included). Women who were pregnant or likely to become pregnant as well as lactating mothers. Those who could not stop drinking coffee or coca cola during the treatment period. This last requirement was included because of a possible interference of these drinks with homeopathic treatment.⁸

Patients and methods

Recruitment

Patients were recruited from the 1995 and 1996 trials. Those who had participated in 1995 were invited to

Trial design, randomization

The study was double-blind and placebo-controlled, with patients being randomized into four groups from two previous populations (1995 and 1996), giving

Figure 1 Overview of the participating patients and their random allocation to *Betula* (B) or placebo (P) groups during the three years 1995, 1996 and 1997. The number of patients in each group is given inside the boxes.

eight different groups altogether (Figure 1). In this way each person would be his or her own control.

The 1995 participants were thus allocated to one of the following four categories: BB, BP, PB, PP, where B = *Betula* and P = placebo, the first letter indicating what they received in 1995, the second what they would receive in 1997.

For the 1996 group the randomization was done similarly, the only difference being that the 1996 code had not been broken. Although the statistician performing the randomization knew the code, the two groups at that time existed only as group A and B. They were consequently randomized into the four groups AA, AB, BB and BA, where A could be either *Betula* or placebo and vice versa for B.

The patients were contacted by letter, and after written confirmation of participation, they were sent the diaries, instructions for use of tablets and a vial with tablets randomly coded with a number. The tablet instructions were the same as in the 1996 trial: 'One tablet a week for 4 weeks; thereafter one tablet when you get symptoms; then wait 12 h before you take the next tablet. If high levels of pollen occur, you can take three tablets each day.' Since all the patients had participated before, they knew the 'rules' concerning avoidance of caffeine, camphor, peppermint, menthol and also, if possible, dentist consultations and surgical operations.^{6,7} They were allowed to use rescue medication including anti-histamines and anti-asthmatics if necessary.

Study diaries

The registration forms were identical to those used in the 1996 study⁷ ie a 10-day diary written by the participants or their parents, scoring the overall allergy symptoms each day on a VAS. In addition, in order to compare each person with his or her earlier response, the 1995 group had to fill in registration forms that were similar to the ones they used in 1995. Here, they scored 17 different symptoms on a scale from 0 to 3. Day one of the registration was when symptoms first occurred, or for asymptomatic persons, day one would be the first day with measurable pollen counts in the air, as broadcast on radio and TV. No diary was kept during the prophylactic period. In addition to symptoms, participants were asked to report the number of trial tablets taken and also the use of rescue medication.

Drug preparation

The tablets were produced by Drogentralen, Gothenburg, Sweden (DCG) according to GMP standards, as detailed previously.⁶ In short, the tablets were sucrose globules impregnated once with a diluted and succussed solution made from a birch pollen extract. (See discussion section. In 1995 and 1996 the tablets were impregnated three times.) This solution had been diluted and succussed 1:99 30

times, to make a homeopathic 30c dilution. The placebo tablets (sucrose globules) were identical to the *Betula* tablets in size, shape, weight and taste.

Pollen counts and weather report

As in the previous studies we recorded the pollen counts and weather reports during the birch pollen season in Oslo (Figure 2).

Statistics

The daily allergy symptom scores were collected from all the participants, using the VAS system. Each participant had only one score for each day. Initially, the registration period was 10 days, but because of small amounts of pollen all participants were asked to continue for as long as possible to obtain data also from days with possibly relevant pollen exposure. The mean value for each person for the whole period was calculated, and this value was compared with the mean value from the previous year. The 1995/1997 participants had a different score system in 1995, based on the mean value of 17 different allergy symptoms. Therefore, we had to transform these values to VAS-values using Z-scores. This is a well known method for standardizing scores.⁹ We made regression plots and Pearsons correlation coefficient was used to assess consistency of responses from one trial to the next, (Figure 3). All statistical analyses were performed before the code was broken.

Ethics

Informed and written consent was obtained from all patients. The study was part of a research program on unconventional medicine under The Research Council of Norway and was approved by the Regional Ethics Committee for Medical Research and also by the Homeopathic Ethical Committee.

Results

Patient characteristics. Allergen exposure

Among 139 persons from two previous studies, 51 were willing to participate in this third trial (Figure 1). Data concerning pollen counts and spring temperatures are shown in Figure 2. The 1997 season had low pollen counts, with symptom-provoking concentrations during only three 2-day periods, much as in 1996. The weather was variable, with some days sunny, some days rainy. The average length of registration period was 22 days.

Randomization and symptom course

Figure 1 gives an overview of the participant allocations in the three different studies. Figure 3 shows a scatter diagram for each of the four groups generated after the codes were broken, depicting all persons'

Figure 2 Overview of the pollen counts and weather conditions during the years 1995, 1996 and 1997.

mean symptom scores during the two pollen seasons when they participated in the study.

A consistent response from the individuals receiving *Betula* during two different years was found, as indicated by a significant relationship between the variables ($r=0.70$, $P=0.003$; Figure 3A). Similarly, the group receiving placebo both years had symptom scores that were significantly correlated during these two periods ($r=0.75$; $P=0.01$; Figure 3B). No significant correlation between accumulated symptom scores, for each of the two pollen seasons, was found for the two groups being differently treated during the two seasons (Figure 3C and D).

Time course of symptom scores

Table 1 compares symptom scores for the two years, for each of the four patient groups. No significant increase occurred in the BP group, nor a decrease in the PB group, which would have been expected if *Betula* medication does alleviate allergic symptoms.

Discussion

The results of the present study are intriguing. The obvious and plausible expectation would be that no difference would be found between the four patient groups. However, we found that those individuals who received *Betula* 30c (B) both years (either in

Table 1 Symptom scores in the four groups during the first and second year of registration

Group	n	Year 1	Year 2
BB	15	2.4 (1.6, 3.1)	2.9 (2.0, 3.7)
PP	10	3.0 (1.8, 4.2)	2.9 (1.1, 4.6)
PB	10	1.2 (0.3, 2.1)	2.0 (1.1, 2.9)
BP	16	1.9 (1.2, 2.6)	2.0 (1.1, 2.8)

Mean VAS values, with their 95% confidence interval in parentheses, are given. No significantly different results in years 1 and 2 were found in any of the four groups. BB: patients receiving *Betula* both years; PP: patients given placebo both years; PB: patients given placebo first year and then *Betula*; BP: patients given *Betula* first year and then placebo.

1995/1997 or in 1996/1997) reacted rather consistently, in the same way as did those receiving placebo (P) during two following years. On the other hand, in the groups where the remedy changed either from *Betula* to placebo or vice versa there was no consistent response.

In the *Betula/Betula* group (BB) we found that those who had a low symptom score the first year, had a low score the second year, and those who had a high score the first year, had a high score the second year (Figure 3A). This could certainly suggest that *Betula* equals placebo, with the low score persons being 'placebo responders'¹⁰⁻¹² and the high score persons being resistant to a placebo effect. The same interpretation could be made for the PP group (Figure 3B). But if *Betula* equals placebo, one should expect such

Figure 3 Scatter diagrams with regression lines showing symptom scores for each patient during two different years, the x-axis denoting first year (1995 or 1996) scores and the y-axis second year (1997) scores. (A) Patients receiving *Betula* both years (BB). (B) Patients given placebo both years (PP). (C) Patients given placebo first year and then *Betula* (PB). (D) Patients given *Betula* first year and then placebo (BP).

results in all four categories of comparison. This was not the case.

The results from the BB groups could also mean that some of the patients experienced a genuine beneficial effect of *Betula* (low score), and those who might have had a negative effect of the remedy the first year (if the theory of aggravation is considered), also had this same negative effect the second year. In other words, this might possibly support the hypothesis that homeopathy does work, but the remedy could have been too 'strong' according to the homeopaths' paradigm.

There were some confounding factors that complicate the interpretation of the present study. First, the *Betula* tablets were impregnated only once in the present study, but three times in the two previous ones. This was due to a change of the routines by the producer, and we were not aware of this before the study had started. Assuming that the tablets can have a beneficial effect, and knowing that faulty impregna-

tion sometimes occurs, the consequence of one single impregnation would be that some participants in the BB group should have been transferred to the BP group and some from the PB group should have been transferred to the PP group. Conceivably, that might have ruined the correlations found, and consequently supported the final conclusion.

Secondly, the low pollen spread was not optimal for the investigation in 1997. Such unpredictability makes allergy studies difficult: is the patient better because pollen exposure declines or because the medication works?

Thirdly, the periods of registration were different, some patients monitored for 10 days, others for 30. Finally, we know very little about how a message like 'please register another week so that we can obtain data' might affect symptoms or signs during a therapeutic trial.

The present study describes how allergic persons rate their allergy symptoms when treated with a homeopathic remedy or placebo during two pollen seasons. We have not been able to find similar studies in the scientific literature. Other kinds of reliability studies on homeopathic treatments have been performed, however, suggesting in fact the existence of reliable responses.¹⁻⁴ Moreover, there are at least two blinded intervention trials of traditional immunotherapy where patients scored their allergy symptoms after treatment and discontinuation with immunotherapy over several years.^{13,14} However, reliability questions or the consistency of each person's symptom scores from year to year were not discussed.

In conclusion, the most plausible interpretation of the present results is that people participating in a trial twice tend to answer in much the same way both times, but this tendency did not, by accident, show up in the two groups where remedies were changed (BP and PB). This could simply be due to the small size of the groups. To achieve positive correlations significantly ($P < 0.05$, two-tailed test) different from zero and with the same regression results as found (Figure 3C and D), 50 persons in group PB and 240 in group BP would have been needed, (power 0.8).

For the same reason, we cannot draw any conclusions about the effect of *Betula* 30c vs placebo from this trial.

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